

Nonlinear Empirical Pricing in Electricity Markets using Fundamental Weather Factors

Stephanía Mosquera-López^{a,*}, Jorge M. Uribe^{b,c}, Diego Fernando Manotas-Duque^a,

^a School of Industrial Engineering, Universidad del Valle, Calle 13 # 100-00, Cali, Colombia.

^b Department of Economics, Universidad del Valle, Calle 13 # 100-00, Cali, Colombia.

^c Riskcenter-University of Barcelona, Av. Diagonal, 690 08034, Barcelona, Spain.

* Corresponding author. E-mail: stephania.mosquera.lopez@correounivalle.edu.co

Date of this version: July 14, 2017.

Abstract

A nonlinear factor model based on fundamental weather variables, in addition to market-related variables, is proposed for modeling the price of electricity. The full conditional distribution of electricity prices using quantile regressions is modeled and the effect of weather factors on upside and downside risks in the electricity market is analyzed. Data from the Nord Pool is used to fit the proposed model to a wide and highly integrated market, as well as several individual national markets, and to search for possible asymmetries in both individual and aggregated levels of the price dynamics. By doing so, important differences across countries and quantiles in the price responses to weather variations are documented, but mostly extensive evidence in favor of the quantile-factor model based on weather variables is provided.

Keywords: electricity; pricing; quantile regression; weather; risk.

1. Introduction and Literature Review

Factor models are currently milestones for the analysis of electricity prices. Both practitioners and academics rely heavily on such models to forecast and explain the dynamics of spot and forward prices. The key point in factor-pricing models is the selection of explanatory factors

to be included in a potential empirical specification. When envisioning factors to include in a pricing equation, the literature can be divided into two streams. On one hand, chosen factors may respond to relative pricing considerations. A famous example of this is the Black-Scholes option-pricing model, in which the value of an option is calculated given the value of an underlying asset. On the other hand, portfolios or single assets can be priced in absolute terms. In this case, each asset is priced by reference to its exposure to fundamental sources of risk, which are generally macroeconomic in nature, at least in the case of bonds and stocks [1].

Here, a nonlinear absolute pricing model for electricity markets based on fundamental factors related to weather is proposed, which is novel to the literature. The main contribution of the research to the field is twofold: first, the convenience of a nonlinear specification and the inclusion of weather factors when analyzing electricity prices is highlighted. Those features are incorporated into a single and comprehensive framework using quantile¹ regressions. Second, a comparison is made on how weather factors affect downside and upside risks (lower and upper quantiles of the prices) faced by agents in the market. In the meantime, several asymmetries that were unnoticed in the previous literature owing to the nonlinear nature of the relationship between weather and electricity prices are discussed.

Weather factors are crucial in the price formation process of electricity markets, as has been emphasized by previous works [2–7]. They underlie other fundamental factors previously explored in the field (mainly related to the market). Weather is a determinant not only because an increasing and significant share of renewable technologies in the process of energy generation (i.e., solar and wind technologies) is very weather sensitive ([8]) but also because demand in energy markets is strongly and clearly associated with weather. Additionally, although the exposure to market-related factors such as consumption can be smoothed through energy storage devices, the impact of weather factors such as temperature is more difficult to anticipate and thus to hedge.

¹ Since a percentile is equal to a quantile when the sample is divided into 100 intervals, the terms are used indistinctly throughout the document.

Hence, weather variables such as temperature, precipitation, wind speed and irradiance are incorporated into the nonlinear setup proposed, adding to the market variables that signal expected consumption and the prices of inputs and substitute goods (as is performed, for instance, by [9]). The model performance substantially improves after the inclusion of weather variables at the different quantiles of the distribution, and indeed, weather variables are significant and determinant for a greater number of markets and quantiles than are market related factors. These findings can be interpreted as weather being a genuine exogenous and structural factor that determines the dynamics of electricity prices and that should be addressed in a nonlinear fashion, as the method proposed here does. That is, weather is always relevant in the price determination of electricity markets, but its influence varies significantly at different conditional quantiles of electricity prices.

The importance of analyzing the entire distribution of electricity prices instead of focusing exclusively on the central fragments, as has been regularly performed in the asset pricing literature of finance and in the fundamental-pricing literature of the energy field, has been recently emphasized by [9–11]². Nevertheless, those authors do not consider weather-related factors in their modeling setup. Given the marked seasonality associated with weather variables, the relationship between these and the energy demand (and therefore energy prices) is expected to differ across the quantiles of the energy price distribution. Therefore, the “betas” in the pricing equation (i.e., the partial correlations of weather factors and prices) will likely experience instabilities across the conditional distribution of prices that must be addressed directly to price the fundamental risk associated with weather in an accurate fashion. With this approach, this research distances itself from previous works in the literature that use weather-related variables to model or forecast electricity prices in a linear setting, seeking to explain the variation of the first or second moments of the electricity price distributions (see Table 1). Furthermore, none of the previous research in the literature has analyzed the joint

² Although quantile regressions have been used only recently to model electricity prices, nonlinearity in these prices is a well-established empirical fact in the literature (see Table 1). For example [16–27] document nonlinearities in electricity prices using diverse methods to address them, such as switching regressions, neural networks and machine learning techniques.

effect of the four relevant weather factors that may affect electricity price dynamics, i.e., temperature, wind speed, precipitation and irradiance, as done herein.

Table 1. Literature review comparative approaches

Reference	Market	Weather Factors				Linear Model				Nonlinear Model		
		Temp	Wind	Preci	Solar	ARMA	GARCH	OLS	Other	MS	CI	QR
[2]	Nordic	*		*				*				
[3]	Scandinavian	*	*	*		*	*					
[8]	EEX		*		*			*				
[4]	EEX		*		*							
[5]	Italian				*			*				
[6]	NEPOOL		*							*		
[7]	Massachusetts				*			*				
[9]	UK											*
[11]	UK							*				*
[10]	UK					*						*
[16]	Nordic										*	
[18]	Europe-US							*			*	
[20]	Nordic										*	
[19]	EEX					*					*	
[17]	PJM										*	
[21]	EEX-OMEL- PJM- NEPOOL										*	
[22]	EEX- NEPOOL- PJM										*	
[27]	Nordic										*	
[23]	OMEL							*				*
[24]	PJM- NEPOOL											*
[25]	PJM											*
[26]	Australian											*

EEX stands for European Energy Exchange (Germany), NEPOOL for New England Power Pool (United States), PJM for Pennsylvania-New Jersey-Maryland Interconnection (United States), and OMEL for *Operador del Mercado Ibérico de Energía* (Spain). Temp stands for temperature, Wind for wind speed, Preci for precipitation,

and Solar for solar energy. The acronym ARMA is Autoregressive Moving Average; GARCH is Generalized AutoRegressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity; OLS is Ordinary Least square; MS is Markov-switching; CI is Computational Intelligence; QR is Quantile Regression.

The performance of the model that accounts for weather factors with one that includes only the previously used market-related factors is compared by means of Wald statistics and the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). All the explanatory variables in the proposed model are lagged; therefore, the model is also well suited to address one-day-ahead price forecasts, which are crucial for empirical applications and for practitioners. However, this is not emphasized in the discussion of the results, in which instead the role of weather as a fundamental factor is highlighted and the induced price dynamics in different quantiles and markets is carefully explained. Moreover, by modeling price dynamics considering the effect of weather factors, price signals become an important input for models of optimization in energy generation systems, such as the one presented in [12].

The proposed model is estimated using data from the Nord Pool day-ahead market (Norway, Sweden, Denmark, Finland, Estonia, Lithuania and Latvia). By fitting the model to the aggregated series of prices and to individual market prices, further asymmetries in the price formation and risk dynamics on the country level are identified. Nevertheless, weather factors remain significant in the vast majority of the analyzed markets and quantiles in the empirical application. The model performs satisfactorily at both, explaining the price dynamics and helping to capture extreme situations related to downside and upside risks in the market due to price variations. It provides relevant insights for market agents who can make informed decisions and design hedging strategies according to the differential effects of weather factors over electricity prices.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section two contains the methodology of factor models and quantile regressions. In section three, the data used is presented and the factors included in the model are described. In section four, the main results in terms of energy price dynamics and risk modeling are discussed. Finally, in section five, conclusions are presented and possible future research lines and limitations of the model are discussed.

2. Methodology: Factor Models and Quantile Regressions

For $i = 1 \dots N$, $t = 1 \dots T$, and $k = 1 \dots K$, where N is the number of variables, T is the number of periods, and K is the number of latent factors, traditional linear factor models are summarized by the following equation:

$$x_{it} = \lambda_{1i}f_{1t} + \dots + \lambda_{Ki}f_{Kt} + e_{it} \quad (1)$$

or more compactly by $\mathbf{x}_t = \boldsymbol{\lambda}_i \mathbf{f}_t + \mathbf{e}_t$ with $\mathbf{x}_t = (x_{1t}, \dots, x_{Nt})'$, $\boldsymbol{\lambda}_i = (\lambda_{1i}, \dots, \lambda_{Ki})$, $\mathbf{f}_t = (f_{1t}, \dots, f_{Kt})'$, and $\mathbf{e}_t = (e_{1t}, \dots, e_{Nt})'$. \mathbf{x}_t is an N -dimensional observable random vector of electricity prices (for either aggregated or individual markets), \mathbf{f}_t is a K -dimensional vector of latent factors, and \mathbf{e}_t is the idiosyncratic error. In the proposed application, this vector includes both weather-driven and market-driven factors (see Table 3). The model in Equation 1 relates the “mean” scenarios in the electricity price distribution with weather and other control factors. However, when analyzing electricity prices, it becomes instrumental, considering nonlinearities in the responses of the electricity prices to movements in any explanatory variable. Accordingly, following the seminal contribution by [13], equation 1 is expanded as follows:

$$q_i^\theta(x_{it} | \mathbf{f}_t; \boldsymbol{\alpha}) = \boldsymbol{\alpha}(\theta)' \mathbf{f}_t, \quad (2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\alpha}(\theta)$ is a vector of coefficients that depends on the quantile θ , q_i^θ . A traditional definition of a quantile is as follows:

$$q_i^\theta = \{x_{it} | \ell_{x_{it}} = 1 - \theta\}, \quad \theta \in (0,1), \quad (3)$$

where $\ell_{x_{it}}$ is a function that indicates what percentage of observations are higher than $\ell_{x_{it}}$ in the sample. Thus, unlike the traditional asset pricing factor theory, which focuses on the average impact of the factor on the endogenous variables, quantile estimates allow the exploration of different fragments of the conditional distribution of electricity prices. Quantile regressions are known to be robust to outliers, and this is of particular importance for analyzing electricity prices, which are plagued by abrupt, short-lived, and generally unanticipated spikes [14].

Regarding the estimation process, if $g_t(\boldsymbol{\alpha}'\mathbf{f}_t)$ is defined, then the θ th quantile regression will be defined as a vector of parameter estimates $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ that solves the following problem:

$$\min_{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T [\theta - I(x_{it} < g_t(\boldsymbol{\alpha}'\mathbf{f}_t))][x_{it} - g_t(\boldsymbol{\alpha}'\mathbf{f}_t)], \quad (4)$$

where $I(\cdot)$ is an indicator function that takes the value of one when the condition is fulfilled and zero otherwise. x_{it} is defined as in equation 1 and separated regressions must be conducted for each i . Quantile regression constitutes a special case of the least absolute deviations estimator (LAD), which is more convenient and robust than the ordinary least squares estimator when the data present heavy tails as is the case for electricity returns. Quantile regressions are also semi-parametric in nature; they require minimal distributional assumptions on the underlying data generating process. Additionally, they offer greater flexibility in the analysis of different scenarios in the electricity markets, which is likely related to distinctive weather conditions. For instance, lower quantiles can be interpreted as extreme situations, in which an abnormally low price is recorded in the market, whereas higher quantiles are naturally related to scarcity prices probably induced by very low temperatures and the subsequent increase in the demand for energy or by the reduction in the market power generation due to an operational failure.

3. Data

The Nord Pool is the leading power market in Europe and one of the biggest integrated markets worldwide. In the day-ahead market (Elspot), producers and consumers make their bids for the delivery of electricity for each hour of the next day. The markets that are part of the Nord Pool are divided into different bidding areas (currently, there are 15 sub-areas plus the total area). The pricing mechanism functions as follows: first, the system establishes the prices for each hour of the following day that balance aggregate supply and aggregate demand; second, according to transmission capacity and congestion, different area prices may be established to solve bottlenecks.

The dataset of dependent variables consists of the day-ahead electricity prices, quoted in EUR/MWh, for the 16 bidding areas (see Table 2) in the Nord Pool market. The dataset of

explanatory variables consists of temperature, wind speed, precipitation, and irradiance for the seven countries that are part of the day-ahead Nord Pool Market, consumption of the bidding areas, natural gas price, coal price, and freight costs. The frequency of the data is daily. The sample period starts on January 1, 2013 and ends on March 30, 2016. The electricity prices and consumption were obtained from the Nord Pool Spot, the irradiance series from SoDa (solar radiation data) Service, and the other explanatory variables from Bloomberg.

Table 2. Bidding areas and acronyms

Area	Description	Area	Description
SYS	System Price	NO1	Oslo
SE1	Luleå	NO2	Kristiansand
SE2	Sundsvall	NO3	Molde, Trondheim
SE3	Stockholm	NO4	Tromsø
SE4	Malmö	NO5	Bergen
FI	Finland	EE	Estonia
DK1	Western Denmark	LV	Latvia
DK2	Eastern Denmark	LT	Lithuania

The analysis is focused on the system price and on single chosen regions within countries that have several bidding areas. Latvia and Lithuania present very similar behavior to each other (see Figure 1), but such dynamics differ greatly from the system’s price and other area prices. These two markets are well interconnected with each other, so the price formation appears to be made in a joint area. However, they present transmission limitations with Estonia, which prevents them from buying cheaper electricity provided by the Nord Pool.

In the case of SE1 and NO1, these areas show a dynamic similar to the system price, which is related to the fact that Norway and Sweden are responsible for 73% of Nordic/Baltic power generation, whereas Latvia and Lithuania represent only 2% of the total generation³. Additionally, Norway, Sweden and Estonia were the only countries that had a supply surplus in 2015.

³ Information retrieved from <http://www.nordpoolspot.com/>

Figure 1. Electricity prices (EUR/MWh), January 2013-March 2016

Note: For each bidding area at any level of confidence, electricity prices are trend stationary.

The explanatory variables, weather-driven and market-driven factors are used in the model setup with one period lagging, as in [9]: the bids that agents make today determine tomorrow's price, so the price is set with the information of the explanatory variables of today.

Four weather factors are constructed using temperature, wind speed, precipitation, and irradiance data for the seven countries of the Nord Pool market (see Figure 2). To use as much information as possible, all weather variable data were aggregated into one factor by means of Principal Components Analysis (PCA). Hence, each factor represents a latent factor of the weather conditions in the Nordic/Baltic area. Table 3 provides a summary of the factors used as explanatory variables in the model proposed herein.

Figure 2. Temperature (degrees Celsius), wind speed (m/s), precipitation (integer in 0.01 mm), irradiance (Wh/m²), January 2013-March 2016

Note: m/s stands for meter per second, mm for millimeter, and Wh/m² for watt-hour per square meter.

Table 3. Description of factors⁴

Variable	Description	Units	Stationarity	PCA
<i>Weather Factors</i>				
Temperature	Daily average temperature for Norway, Sweden, Finland, Denmark, Estonia, Lithuania and Latvia.	Degrees Celsius	The series are stationary.	Explains 95.60% of the total variation of the data.
Wind Speed	Daily average wind speed for Norway, Sweden, Finland, Denmark, Estonia, Lithuania and Latvia.	m/s	The series are trend-stationary.	Explains 68.29% of the total variation of the data.
Precipitation	Daily average precipitation for Norway, Sweden, Finland, Denmark, Estonia, Lithuania and Latvia.	Integer in 100th mm	The series are stationary.	Explains 54.44% of the total variation of the data.
Irradiance	Daily average irradiance (global irradiation on horizontal plane at ground level) for Norway, Sweden, Finland, Denmark, Estonia, Lithuania and Latvia.	Wh/m ²	The series present a stochastic trend.	Explains 92.36% of the total variation of the data.
<i>Market Factors</i>				
Consumption	Daily total for the 15 bidding areas.	MWh	The series present a stochastic trend.	Explains 87.16% of the total variation of the data.
Natural Gas Price	NGUSHHUB Index: natural gas for next-day delivery at the Henry Hub.	Index	The series presents a stochastic trend.	-
Coal Price	API2 index: steam coal delivered to the ARA region of Northwest Europe.	Index	The series presents a stochastic trend.	-
Freight Costs	Baltic Dry Index: A composite of the Baltic Capesize, Panamax, Handysize and Supramax indices.	Index	The series presents a stochastic trend.	-

Note: The source of the data is Bloomberg, except for the consumption of the bidding areas, which was retrieved from the Nord Pool Spot, and the irradiance that was retrieved from SoDa Service. The transformation of the series that display a stochastic trend is the logarithmic returns, except for the consumption series, which were

⁴ The unit root test used is the Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test, and the results are available upon request.

aggregated by PCA. The first principal component of the consumption data is stationary. m/s stands for meter per second, mm for millimeter, and Wh/m² for watt-hour per square meter.

Lastly, Table 4 presents the Nordic power generation matrix. Hydropower is the base of the system with a participation of 57% of the total electricity produced. That is, the demand of electricity is first met with the production from hydroelectric plants, which have the lowest production marginal cost. The other sources of production enter stepwise in the generation, once the demand cannot be fully met with the cheapest technology, according to their marginal costs. The last technologies to enter in the generation of electricity are thermal plants that have a participation of 10% in the generation matrix and have the highest production marginal costs.

Table 4. Nordic Power Generation Matrix 2012

Energy Source	Norway	Sweden	Denmark	Finland	Total	% Share
Hydropower	142.9	77.7	0.0	16.7	237.3	57%
Nuclear Power	0.0	61.2	0.0	22.1	83.3	20%
Fossil Fuels	3.4	4.6	16.4	17.1	41.5	10%
Wind Power	1.6	7.1	10.3	0.5	19.5	5%
Other Renewable	0.0	10.8	12.5	10.4	33.7	8%
Non-identifiable	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.9	0.9	0%
Total	147.8	161.6	39.2	67.7	416.3	100%

Note: Own elaboration with information from Nordic Production Split 2004-2012. The units of generation are in TWh (terawatt-hour).

4. Results and Discussion

The factor model proposed was estimated at different quantiles of the distribution of electricity prices (from the 5th to the 95th percentiles) for all the bidding areas within the markets of Norway, Sweden, Finland, Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania and for the integrated market of the Nord Pool. The performance of the model that includes weather factors is always superior compared with one that includes only market-related factors. The main results for the integrated market are summarized in Figure 3. Additionally, a comparative plot among the markets in the Nord Pool is presented in Figure 4.

4.1. Statistical Performance of the Model

The model that includes both weather and market factors was compared with a model that excludes weather factors, by means of Wald statistics. Each Wald test was computed as in [15]. Under the null hypothesis, the slopes of the weather factors (β_2) are not statistically significant ($H_0: \beta_2 = 0$). For all the percentiles and for all the prices (except for Estonia area price (EE) at the fifth quantile), the null hypothesis is rejected at any level of confidence (see Table 5). Therefore, statistically, the proposed model always outperforms an alternative setup where no weather factors are considered.

Table 5. Wald Test Results

Percentile	SYS		SE1		FI		DK1	
	F-value	P-value	F-value	P-value	F-value	P-value	F-value	P-value
0.05	8.23	0.00	8.31	0.00	4.64	0.00	6.55	0.00
0.10	8.64	0.00	8.93	0.00	5.17	0.00	23.09	0.00
0.15	9.07	0.00	8.68	0.00	21.01	0.00	18.11	0.00
0.20	17.77	0.00	12.09	0.00	16.26	0.00	23.32	0.00
0.25	47.19	0.00	21.28	0.00	15.91	0.00	14.40	0.00
0.30	26.61	0.00	14.68	0.00	16.85	0.00	18.47	0.00
0.35	42.28	0.00	31.47	0.00	18.91	0.00	25.60	0.00
0.40	34.91	0.00	29.34	0.00	15.81	0.00	25.27	0.00
0.45	23.74	0.00	33.64	0.00	14.29	0.00	22.48	0.00
0.50	17.55	0.00	21.93	0.00	17.83	0.00	22.08	0.00
0.55	16.56	0.00	21.03	0.00	12.05	0.00	21.69	0.00
0.60	14.99	0.00	19.13	0.00	12.99	0.00	19.77	0.00
0.65	19.93	0.00	19.30	0.00	24.68	0.00	16.47	0.00
0.70	19.92	0.00	17.14	0.00	22.41	0.00	14.82	0.00
0.75	15.60	0.00	24.05	0.00	23.65	0.00	21.67	0.00
0.80	24.24	0.00	22.09	0.00	23.85	0.00	22.58	0.00
0.85	34.80	0.00	38.52	0.00	20.58	0.00	28.18	0.00
0.90	23.50	0.00	16.41	0.00	23.02	0.00	19.79	0.00
0.95	28.51	0.00	13.39	0.00	7.54	0.00	11.18	0.00

Percentile	NO1		EE		LV		LT	
	F-value	P-value	F-value	P-value	F-value	P-value	F-value	P-value
0.05	11.56	0.00	1.68	0.15	27.51	0.00	52.79	0.00
0.10	21.50	0.00	18.08	0.00	34.31	0.00	31.84	0.00
0.15	31.99	0.00	10.87	0.00	40.40	0.00	51.40	0.00
0.20	26.24	0.00	14.34	0.00	40.90	0.00	39.71	0.00
0.25	41.09	0.00	20.49	0.00	32.92	0.00	36.00	0.00
0.30	41.65	0.00	16.53	0.00	39.41	0.00	40.55	0.00
0.35	62.32	0.00	20.70	0.00	36.64	0.00	41.74	0.00
0.40	38.90	0.00	19.49	0.00	36.31	0.00	35.75	0.00
0.45	30.53	0.00	16.86	0.00	29.39	0.00	28.90	0.00
0.50	12.72	0.00	19.37	0.00	25.19	0.00	26.93	0.00
0.55	20.14	0.00	19.75	0.00	25.04	0.00	23.37	0.00
0.60	27.53	0.00	21.12	0.00	25.08	0.00	21.50	0.00
0.65	33.29	0.00	20.10	0.00	24.75	0.00	24.19	0.00
0.70	38.92	0.00	27.26	0.00	22.00	0.00	21.68	0.00
0.75	27.90	0.00	20.64	0.00	24.26	0.00	20.46	0.00
0.80	32.77	0.00	19.37	0.00	19.35	0.00	20.20	0.00
0.85	43.30	0.00	13.00	0.00	20.36	0.00	32.30	0.00
0.90	55.95	0.00	16.02	0.00	16.57	0.00	17.53	0.00
0.95	28.89	0.00	16.53	0.00	16.42	0.00	25.66	0.00

Additionally, for each model, the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) was estimated in order to select the model that best fits the data. The model specification that includes both weather and market factors has for each of the 304 estimated regressions (16 prices, 19 percentiles) a smaller AIC, indicating that this specification must be selected in all cases for modeling the electricity prices (the results are presented in the Appendix).

4.2. Effects of the Weather Factors at Different Percentiles of Electricity Prices

Figure 3. Effects of weather and control variables on electricity prices at different percentiles of the price distribution for the system price (SYS)⁵

Note: The horizontal axis in each subplot corresponds to a quantile of electricity prices, from the 5th to the 95th percentile, while the vertical axis corresponds to the effect of the variable on the electricity prices. The dotted black lines show the varying effects across percentiles, with their respective confidence intervals displayed as shadowed areas. The red solid line is the effect at the median of the price distribution, which has associated confidence intervals shown as red dotted lines. All the confidence intervals were constructed with 95% confidence. The variables are defined as follows: XTEMPERATURE is the temperature factor constructed by aggregating daily average temperature from each country; XPRECIPITATION is the precipitation factor constructed by aggregating daily average precipitation from each country; XWIND.SPEED is the wind speed factor constructed by aggregating the daily average wind speed from each country; XIRRADIANCE is the irradiance factor constructed by aggregating the daily average irradiance from each country, XAPI2 is the coal price index; XBDIY is the freight cost index; XNGUSHHUB is the natural gas price index; and

⁵ The detailed results for individual markets are available upon request.

XCONSUMPTION is the demand factor constructed by aggregating the daily consumption from each bidding area.

4.2.1. Effects of temperature (on an aggregated level)

Although the effects of temperature are always negative, as expected, these are more pronounced when the prices are very low (below the 20th percentile) or very high (above the 90th percentile). The differences with respect to the “median effect” (red straight line) are statistically significant, as evidenced by the fact that these “percentile effects” are not included in the median confidence interval (dotted lines around the median effect) for considerable fragments of the price distribution.

The situation described above can be rationalized as follows. When electricity prices are relatively low, one may expect greater price elasticity of the energy demand and thus a higher sensitivity of prices to changes in this explanatory variable. Higher temperatures imply lower heating requirements, which translates into lower prices. In this situation, consumers may decide to reduce their energy demand following a price increase. Such situation allows more flexibility than those in which heating is not optional and a corresponding effect on prices is more pronounced.

In contrast, at the highest quantiles (above the 90th percentile), the documented effects are likely associated with price spikes that follow unanticipated “supply shocks.” For instance, a shortage in power generation is due to the impossibility of using hydropower generation sources, which is likely the case when the temperature drops below zero degrees. This makes it necessary to resort to alternative energy sources such as wind power and thermal plants. These alternatives, in turn, are very weather dependent in the case of wind, or they depend on inputs such as gas and oil that are known to display very volatile prices, which is the case for thermal power generation technologies. In this situation, a reduction in the temperature (which is already likely at a very low level to start with) translates to dramatic changes in electricity prices, which depend on the alternative power sources available to substitute for hydropower generation.

In regular situations, the price changes that follow a reduction or an increment in the temperature are closer to zero, and indeed, for the quantiles around the 50th percentile they are statistically indistinguishable from zero. Those situations are related to relatively inelastic demands and a more stable power generation provided by the system. Overall, very different effects of temperature on electricity prices are documented, ranging from very significant at the tails of the price distribution to unnoticeable at its center.

4.2.2. Effects of wind speed (on an aggregated level)

In the case of wind speed, the effect is always negative, independent of the quantiles of the price distribution. That is, an increase in wind speed always leads to a reduction in the price of electricity. This result is also quite intuitive because wind constitutes an increasingly crucial input for power generation. Nevertheless, the effects seem governed by two different regimes, conditional on the price percentiles. For prices below the 40th percentile, the effect associated with variations in wind speed is small (although statistically significant), while it is higher at higher prices. Since wind is an alternative power generating technology that becomes more important as the other technologies begin to decline, it is natural that its effects on the electricity prices become more pronounced while moving up across the quantiles of the distribution. In other words, an increment in wind speed is more crucial to the markets in situations of relative shortage of supply, as signaled by higher prices, than in situations of relative market surplus. Note as well that the effects measured by the quantile estimates are very similar to the median effects above the 40th percentile.

4.2.3. Effects of precipitation (on an aggregated level)

The effects of precipitation on the price dynamics are much more stable compared with those of the other weather variables, but they are statistically equal to zero for most of the quantiles, except between the 40th and the 60th percentiles. For this reason, not to interpret the coefficients associated with this weather variable is preferred.

4.2.4. Effects of irradiance (on an aggregated level)

Irradiance has a statically significant effect on prices above the 40th percentile, and this effect differs from the median effect. When the prices are relatively stable, in the 40th-70th percentile, higher solar energy translates into a price decrease, as expected. However, in the higher quantiles, the relation between irradiance and prices becomes positive, which indicates that higher solar energy is correlated with higher prices. This effect can be explained by the electric generation matrix that Nordic market houses: the participation of renewable energies, such as solar, is low, which indicates that when prices are high (low supply or high demand), higher irradiance levels do not stabilize the price, and the system must continue to produce with the technologies available, which in turn present higher costs.

4.2.5. Effects of other control, market-related variables (on an aggregated level)

Consumption has a significant and nonlinear effect on electricity prices. The main nonlinearities are documented at the highest quantiles (above the 75th percentile), at which the estimated effects become more pronounced. [9] also document more pronounced effects and higher variability in periods of higher demand.

Additionally, it is found that natural gas prices have a positive effect on the electricity prices at almost all percentiles. Around the 60th to the 80th percentiles, natural gas prices affect electricity prices with increasing strength. In the case of coal prices, as expected, they also have a positive effect on electricity prices. However, they present non-statistically significant and linear effects at almost all percentiles.

Lastly, freight costs have a positive effect on electricity prices from the 40th percentile upward, as expected. This effect is statistically significant above the 50th percentile and very similar to the median effect. This means that when prices are high, thermal plants must be turned on and, as a consequence, the importance of substitute goods (such as natural gas and coal) increments and freight costs become relevant. The higher the costs of these goods, the higher the prices for the median and higher quantiles.

4.3. Comparative analysis between Nord Pool markets

Figure 4 shows the effects of weather factors for different area prices. Weather betas associated with the markets of Sweden and Norway are remarkably similar to the already described effects for the integrated market. This is expected given the relative size of these two markets with respect to the integrated system. For the case of Denmark, which houses a power generation matrix highly dependent on wind power (see Table 4), the effects of temperature are less pronounced and more stable across quantiles compared with Norway or Sweden. This follows because greater independence on hydropower generation sources helps the market to isolate its prices from the effects of temperature variations. However, it is precisely for the same reason that wind speed is so crucial to Denmark's market. Moreover, the effect of irradiance over this market tends not to be statistically significant and stable over all the quantiles. The markets of Finland and Estonia display similar patterns to those of the Danish market.

Figure 4. Comparative effects of weather on the electricity prices across quantiles and national markets

Note: The figure shows the effects of weather variables on the prices of the representative bidding areas of the day-ahead Nord Pool market and on the system price. The effects vary according to the quantile.

Latvia and Lithuania merit a separate analysis. Temperature positively affects their electricity prices across all the percentiles of their price distributions. This unexpected effect may be related to the limitations on transmission capacity of these countries: their connection to the Nord Pool makes it difficult to buy cheaper electricity when they require more of it. Instead, they tend to connect to the Nord Pool as a price stabilization mechanism during more regular situations. In the case of wind speed, this factor has an expected negative effect on these prices, and indeed, such an effect is higher across almost all the percentiles of the price distribution compared with the other areas within the Nord Pool. Lastly, irradiance always has a negative effect over the price dynamics, which means that for these countries higher solar energy always translates into lower prices.

4.4. Significance of Weather Factors and Relative Performance

Table 6 summarizes the significance levels of the weather and market factors included in the regressions of the proposed model. Wind speed and temperature are statistically significant in the great majority of cases, more frequently than all other factors included in the model. That is, they are significant in 83% and 71%, respectively, of the total 304 estimated regressions (16 prices, 19 percentiles).

Table 6. Summary of the Factors' Significance

Variable	Significance %
Intercept	93%
Wind Speed	83%
Temperature	71%
BDIY	52%
Consumption	50%
NGUSHHUB	40%
Irradiance	38%
Precipitation	26%
API21MON	16%

Note: Each percentage corresponds to the number of times that each factor (explanatory variable) is statistically significant.

4.5. Analysis of Extreme Percentiles

Figure 5 shows the betas associated with temperature against the betas that correspond to wind speed for extreme percentiles: 0.10 and 0.90; 0.05 and 0.95; and 0.01 and 0.99⁶. In this way, it aims to highlight the dynamics that underlie the relationship between the exposures to these weather factors in different markets within the Nord Pool and to provide a direct estimation of upside and downside risks in such markets.

At low percentiles, the sensitivity of the prices to temperature tends to be higher than the sensitivity to wind speed. (The temperature betas' median lies between -1 and -2, while the wind speed betas' median is around -0.5.) The betas of the areas tend to group around the median values and to display a relatively high sensitivity to temperature and low elasticity in relation to wind speed, except for those of Denmark (DK1 and DK2), Finland (FI) and Estonia (EE), which are very sensitive to wind speed and almost insensitive to temperature. The closer to the end of the lower tail, the greater the betas cluster. The exceptions, again, are the cases of Denmark, Finland and Estonia, for which the betas are further dispersed and more sensitive to alternative power sources such as wind power.

⁶ Temperature and wind speed are the two weather factors that are most consistently significant across quantiles and market areas. From this analysis, the results for Latvia and Lithuania are excluded due to the unexpected effects of temperature on their electricity prices (see section 4.3).

In the case of high percentiles, that is, for a situation with relatively high prices, the sensitivity of the prices to temperature tends to be similar to the sensitivity to wind speed. However, in comparison to lower percentiles, the dispersion of the coordinates is higher along the two dimensions, and the size of the effects is also larger. The closer to the end of the tail, the more disperse the risk statistics associated with the markets are. This situation is natural given that higher prices are associated with greater demand requirements for the network, which in turn, implies higher power transmission requirements that cannot always be optimally addressed due to the imperfect nature of any power transmission system.

Additionally, since downside risk (low prices) is linked to producers' risk and upside risk (high prices) to consumers' risk, a direct interpretation of the results is that depending on the area where consumers are located, their risk exposure to weather factors differs greatly. Producers tend to face a more homogeneous risk, regardless of their location.

5. Conclusions

An empirical model for electricity prices is constructed using weather factors in addition to market factors. Weather factors induce a significant and nonlinear influence on electricity prices, which varies depending on the conditional percentile of the prices. Temperature and wind speed are the most relevant factors when analyzing the cross-section of countries that comprise the Nord Pool market. As expected, the main influence of weather occurs at the tails of the electricity price distribution, where abnormally high and low prices – particularly the highest prices – are recorded. These findings are rationalized by assimilating the extreme lowest quantiles as situations of a high elasticity of demand and extreme highest quantiles as situations of supply shortage, in which alternative power generation sources with alternative costs may be used to supply the market, producing spikes of short duration in the price dynamics.

Nevertheless, important asymmetries among the price dynamics in the Nord Pool are also documented. Although Norway and Sweden lead the market, Denmark, Finland and Estonia comprise a relatively homogeneous group in which the effect of temperature, wind speed, and irradiance is less pronounced and more stable across the percentiles of the price

distributions. For the case of Denmark, however, wind speed gains a fundamental importance in the determination of prices, particularly at the highest percentiles.

The influence of market factors seems more homogeneous and less significant across the percentiles of the price distributions than that of the weather factors, which can be interpreted as supportive evidence of weather as a genuine fundamental and structural factor that underlies the dynamics of electricity markets.

Relevant implications for participants of both spot and future markets are also found by analyzing the risk exposure of extreme percentiles to weather factors. When prices are high, weather factors such as temperature and wind speed more diversely affect each area price than when prices are relatively low. These findings have obvious implications for derivatives valuation, and they provide relevant insights for the design of hedging strategies to the agents within the market. Agents' hedging schemes should consider weather factors' inherent volatility, for example, by defining different hedging levels according to different weather regimes. Additionally, consumers and producers should have differentiated hedging strategies since weather factors do not affect homogeneously high and low prices.

The model in hand may be easily extended as to provide a framework for short-term forecasting applications of electricity price quantiles. That is, although it does not provide a direct short-term forecasting of the average-prices, as is generally the case in forecasting models, it does provide a way to forecast different quantiles of the distribution of electricity prices (including the median). For this, it would be necessary either: i) to forecast the weather variables at the right-hand-side of the model, on the horizon of interest, and then using these forecasted series as inputs in the model proposed here. Or ii) to estimate the model using lagged weather variables, which could be then used to construct a direct forecast of the electricity prices quantiles one (or many) periods ahead, as required. Nevertheless, at its current state the model aims to explain electricity price dynamics through weather factors and, in this way, to capture extreme situations related to downside and upside risks in the market due to weather variations, rather than to forecast the quantile series of electricity prices. The causal exercise that we conducted using our model provides relevant insights for market agents who can make informed decisions and design hedging strategies according to

the differential effects of weather factors over electricity prices, at the different quantiles of the price distribution.

A limitation of this study is that demand and supply shocks are not separated from one another. The direct effect of weather factors over electricity prices, controlled by market factors, is analyzed. This is possible due to weather being a completely exogenous factor, which enables the modeling of its relationship with the prices directly. However, future research lines could focus on estimating demand and supply elasticities to differentiate how much of the effect comes from each side of the market.

Acknowledgments:

The support received from the Spanish Ministry of Science/ FEDER ECO2016 -76203-C2-2-P is acknowledged by the author Jorge M. Uribe.

References

- [1] Cochrane JH. Asset pricing. Princeton University Press; 2005.
- [2] Vehviläinen I, Pyykkönen T. Stochastic factor model for electricity spot price - the case of the Nordic market. *Energy Econ* 2005;27:351–67. doi:10.1016/j.eneco.2005.01.002.
- [3] Huurman C, Ravazzolo F, Zhou C. The power of weather. *Comput Stat Data Anal* 2012;56:3793–807. doi:10.1016/j.csda.2010.06.021.
- [4] Paraschiv F, Erni D, Pietsch R. The impact of renewable energies on EEX day-ahead electricity prices. *Energy Policy J* 2014;73:196–210.
- [5] Gulli F, Balbo A Lo. The impact of intermittently renewable energy on Italian wholesale electricity prices: Additional benefits or additional costs? *Energy Policy* 2015;83:123–37. doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2015.04.001.
- [6] Brancucci Martinez-Anido C, Brinkman G, Hodge B-M. The impact of wind power on electricity prices. *Renew Energy* 2016;94:474–87. doi:10.1016/j.renene.2016.03.053.
- [7] Kaufmann RK, Vaid D. Lower electricity prices and greenhouse gas emissions due to

- rooftop solar: empirical results for Massachusetts. *Energy Policy* 2016;93:345–52. doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2016.03.006.
- [8] Adaduldah N, Dorsman A, Franx GJ, Pottuijt P. The influence of renewables on the German day ahead electricity prices. *Perspect. Energy Risk*, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg; 2014, p. 165–82. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-41596-8.
- [9] Hagfors LI, Bunn D, Kristoffersen E, Staver TT, Westgaard S. Modeling the UK electricity price distributions using quantile regression. *Energy* 2016;102:231–43. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2016.02.025.
- [10] Maciejowska K, Nowotarski J, Weron R. Probabilistic forecasting of electricity spot prices using Factor Quantile Regression Averaging. *Int J Forecast* 2016;32:957–65. doi:10.1016/j.ijforecast.2014.12.004.
- [11] Bunn D, Andresen A, Chen D, Westgaard S. Analysis and forecasting of electricity price risks with quantile factor models. *Energy J* 2016;37. doi:DOI: 10.5547/01956574.37.1.dbun.
- [12] Abbassi R, Chebbi S. Energy management strategy for a grid-connected wind-solar hybrid system with battery storage: policy for optimizing conventional energy generation. *Int Rev Electr Eng* 2012;7:3979–90.
- [13] Koenker RW, Bassett G. Regression Quantiles. *Econometrica* 1978;46:33–50. doi:10.2307/1913643.
- [14] Weron R. Electricity price forecasting: A review of the state-of-the-art with a look into the future. *Int J Forecast* 2014;30:1030–81. doi:10.1016/j.ijforecast.2014.08.008.
- [15] Koenker R, Bassett G. Tests of linear hypotheses and l^1 estimation. *Econometrica* 1982;50:1577–84.
- [16] Bierbrauer M, Trück S, Weron R. Modeling electricity prices with regime switching models. *Lect. Notes Comput. Sci.*, vol. 3039, Springer Berlin Heidelberg; 2004, p. 859–867.
- [17] Mount T, Ning Y, Cai X. Predicting price spikes in electricity markets using a regime-switching model with time-varying parameters. *Energy Econ* 2006;28:62–80. doi:10.1016/j.eneco.2005.09.008.

- [18] De Jong C. The nature of power spikes: A regime-switch approach. *Stud Nonlinear Dyn Econom* 2006;10:Article 3. doi:10.2202/1558-3708.1361.
- [19] Kosater P, Mosler K. Can Markov regime-switching models improve power-price forecasts? Evidence from German daily power prices. *Appl Energy* 2006;83:943–58. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2005.10.007.
- [20] Haldrup N, Orregaard M. A regime switching long memory model for electricity prices. *J Econom* 2006;135:349–76. doi:10.1016/j.jeconom.2005.07.021.
- [21] Weron R. Heavy-tails and regime-switching in electricity prices. *Math Methods Oper Res* 2009;69:457–73. doi:10.1007/s00186-008-0247-4.
- [22] Janczura J, Weron R. An empirical comparison of alternate regime-switching models for electricity spot prices. *Energy Econ* 2010;32:1059–73. doi:10.1016/j.eneco.2010.05.008.
- [23] Coelho LDS, Santos AAP. A RBF neural network model with GARCH errors: Application to electricity price forecasting. *Electr Power Syst Res* 2011;81:74–83. doi:10.1016/j.epsr.2010.07.015.
- [24] Singhal D, Swarup KS. Electricity price forecasting using artificial neural networks. *Int J Electr Power Energy Syst* 2011;33:550–5. doi:10.1016/j.ijepes.2010.12.009.
- [25] Amjady N, Keynia F. A new neural network approach to short term load forecasting of electrical power systems. *Energies* 2011;4:488–503. doi:10.3390/en4030488.
- [26] Chen X, Dong ZY, Meng K, Xu Y, Wong KP, Ngan HW. Electricity price forecasting with extreme learning machine and bootstrapping. *IEEE Trans Power Syst* 2012;27:2055–62. doi:10.1109/TPWRS.2012.2190627.
- [27] Cifter A. Forecasting electricity price volatility with the Markov-switching GARCH model: Evidence from the Nordic electric power market. *Electr Power Syst Res* 2013;102:61–7. doi:10.1016/j.epsr.2013.04.007.

Appendix. Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) estimates

Percentile	SYS		SE1		SE2		SE3	
	No W-F	W-F						
0.05	9,183	9,093	9,365	9,278	9,365	9,278	9,406	9,330
0.10	9,068	8,980	9,281	9,198	9,282	9,198	9,300	9,234
0.15	8,962	8,882	9,183	9,117	9,183	9,117	9,191	9,139
0.20	8,880	8,789	9,088	9,032	9,089	9,033	9,099	9,052
0.25	8,806	8,734	9,007	8,968	9,008	8,968	9,025	8,990
0.30	8,753	8,700	8,944	8,920	8,945	8,920	8,971	8,944
0.35	8,722	8,677	8,909	8,877	8,910	8,877	8,940	8,903
0.40	8,705	8,651	8,887	8,834	8,887	8,833	8,917	8,859
0.45	8,693	8,628	8,864	8,802	8,863	8,800	8,896	8,829
0.50	8,687	8,613	8,851	8,781	8,850	8,780	8,886	8,814
0.55	8,686	8,610	8,852	8,780	8,850	8,779	8,889	8,806
0.60	8,695	8,608	8,863	8,779	8,862	8,778	8,903	8,804
0.65	8,709	8,614	8,882	8,784	8,881	8,783	8,917	8,812
0.70	8,722	8,626	8,902	8,799	8,901	8,798	8,940	8,836
0.75	8,747	8,639	8,937	8,830	8,936	8,829	8,983	8,874
0.80	8,792	8,653	9,000	8,875	9,000	8,874	9,060	8,934
0.85	8,872	8,695	9,109	8,957	9,108	8,956	9,184	9,038
0.90	9,011	8,796	9,278	9,113	9,278	9,112	9,373	9,215
0.95	9,295	9,005	9,562	9,398	9,562	9,397	9,692	9,530

Percentile	SE4		FI		DK1		DK2	
	No W-F	W-F	No W-F	W-F	No W-F	W-F	No W-F	W-F
0.05	9,470	9,394	9,436	9,367	9,699	9,545	9,581	9,423
0.10	9,365	9,299	9,142	9,078	9,503	9,363	9,385	9,272
0.15	9,236	9,197	8,956	8,863	9,356	9,243	9,230	9,157
0.20	9,134	9,095	8,822	8,735	9,239	9,149	9,116	9,055
0.25	9,051	9,027	8,728	8,640	9,159	9,075	9,043	8,979
0.30	8,998	8,979	8,660	8,568	9,105	9,016	8,995	8,920
0.35	8,960	8,924	8,605	8,524	9,073	8,982	8,968	8,882
0.40	8,927	8,876	8,565	8,490	9,053	8,963	8,944	8,854
0.45	8,905	8,843	8,537	8,468	9,046	8,955	8,930	8,837
0.50	8,895	8,829	8,525	8,462	9,051	8,957	8,926	8,839
0.55	8,902	8,820	8,528	8,470	9,064	8,972	8,939	8,847
0.60	8,915	8,822	8,548	8,489	9,095	8,998	8,966	8,866
0.65	8,929	8,837	8,585	8,521	9,139	9,042	9,001	8,902
0.70	8,953	8,865	8,642	8,575	9,199	9,103	9,046	8,948
0.75	9,002	8,902	8,731	8,658	9,279	9,184	9,115	9,007
0.80	9,084	8,964	8,868	8,781	9,402	9,293	9,212	9,094
0.85	9,204	9,075	9,057	8,950	9,580	9,464	9,336	9,221
0.90	9,382	9,265	9,323	9,194	9,839	9,725	9,495	9,402
0.95	9,673	9,543	9,766	9,602	10,357	10,254	9,787	9,676

Percentile	NO1		NO2		NO3		NO4	
	No W-F	W-F						
0.05	9,092	8,983	9,047	8,953	9,343	9,263	9,311	9,226
0.10	9,021	8,884	8,979	8,858	9,257	9,167	9,249	9,153
0.15	8,957	8,820	8,922	8,791	9,152	9,070	9,177	9,077
0.20	8,900	8,769	8,867	8,738	9,044	8,980	9,098	9,013
0.25	8,849	8,730	8,814	8,693	8,945	8,909	9,015	8,953
0.30	8,811	8,710	8,774	8,671	8,876	8,847	8,947	8,907
0.35	8,788	8,703	8,747	8,662	8,833	8,800	8,901	8,871
0.40	8,783	8,709	8,739	8,665	8,801	8,753	8,862	8,822
0.45	8,789	8,717	8,743	8,667	8,771	8,716	8,822	8,774
0.50	8,797	8,716	8,748	8,663	8,755	8,693	8,797	8,740
0.55	8,807	8,724	8,754	8,670	8,752	8,688	8,785	8,725
0.60	8,819	8,739	8,762	8,685	8,763	8,683	8,786	8,711
0.65	8,838	8,748	8,777	8,694	8,782	8,682	8,794	8,700
0.70	8,862	8,755	8,795	8,701	8,805	8,695	8,809	8,700
0.75	8,893	8,764	8,820	8,708	8,840	8,720	8,834	8,713
0.80	8,948	8,775	8,869	8,715	8,903	8,764	8,884	8,741
0.85	9,049	8,818	8,964	8,743	9,012	8,845	8,977	8,801
0.90	9,214	8,910	9,129	8,815	9,184	8,996	9,136	8,926
0.95	9,504	9,130	9,422	9,001	9,473	9,272	9,385	9,181

Percentile	NO5		EE		LV		LT	
	No W-F	W-F	No W-F	W-F	No W-F	W-F	No W-F	W-F
0.05	9,079	8,981	9,346	9,286	9,521	9,321	9,584	9,365
0.10	9,006	8,880	9,035	8,967	9,341	9,147	9,394	9,179
0.15	8,946	8,814	8,870	8,805	9,248	9,043	9,294	9,069
0.20	8,888	8,760	8,771	8,702	9,186	8,975	9,216	8,995
0.25	8,833	8,715	8,705	8,627	9,132	8,930	9,154	8,949
0.30	8,792	8,690	8,661	8,585	9,082	8,902	9,090	8,912
0.35	8,764	8,680	8,633	8,561	9,048	8,893	9,052	8,897
0.40	8,755	8,683	8,619	8,548	9,038	8,900	9,042	8,901
0.45	8,760	8,685	8,624	8,549	9,051	8,922	9,051	8,919
0.50	8,765	8,681	8,640	8,565	9,080	8,959	9,073	8,949
0.55	8,772	8,687	8,668	8,593	9,126	9,006	9,110	8,993
0.60	8,780	8,703	8,711	8,639	9,185	9,066	9,164	9,050
0.65	8,799	8,716	8,775	8,707	9,266	9,142	9,241	9,121
0.70	8,825	8,728	8,864	8,796	9,371	9,235	9,344	9,213
0.75	8,862	8,742	8,997	8,908	9,507	9,354	9,481	9,332
0.80	8,919	8,760	9,172	9,058	9,674	9,508	9,656	9,485
0.85	9,024	8,793	9,384	9,252	9,884	9,710	9,873	9,688
0.90	9,197	8,875	9,679	9,520	10,182	10,001	10,174	9,983
0.95	9,504	9,052	10,154	9,976	10,737	10,516	10,736	10,502

Note: No W-F corresponds to the model specification where no weather-factors are included, while W-F corresponds to the model specification with both weather-factors and market-related factors.